

SECReTOUR
Sustainable Creative Tourism

Deliverable

Good practices repository

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Sustainable, Engaging and CREative Tourism as a driver for a better future in rural and remote areas

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Culture, creativity and inclusive society

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2024 SECReTour

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Change Log			
Version	Date	Author	Reason for Change
1.0	19/05/2025	Gábor Oláh (ELTE), Maurizio Toscano (EACHTRA)	First draft, internal review of the content

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Executive summary

The SECReTour Good Practices Repository is a central outcome of WP5, designed to collect, organize, and share solution-oriented practices that promote sustainable cultural tourism in rural and remote areas. Built on a mixed approach, it documents both entire initiatives and their specific practices, drawing from pilot factsheets, external submissions, and cross-work package collaboration. The repository is structured into initiative-level factsheets and a searchable database of good practices, offering a flexible yet coherent framework. Accessible via a user-friendly interface on the project website (<https://secretourproject.eu/goodpractices>), it serves as both a knowledge resource and, in a later phase of the WP, a practical means to support cross-border cooperation, policy development, and the wider adoption of effective tourism practices across macro-regions.

1. Introduction

This deliverable outlines the rationale behind the creation of the SECReTour Good Practices Repository, as well as its structure and initial content. The browsable online collection of good practices has been publicly available since May 2025 at: <https://secretourproject.eu/goodpractices>.

As the first deliverable of WP5, this document advances its core objectives by consolidating insights from other project phases (WP1, WP2, WP3, WP4) and pilot activities to develop the SECReTour Good Practices Repository (Task 5.1). It will also contribute to Task 5.2, for developing recommendations for cross-border cooperation. Drawing on outcomes from WP1 and WP3, a workshop will be designed to promote Fair, Creative, and Sustainable Cultural Tourism (FaCS-Tourism) in rural and remote areas. The results of this workshop will inform the development of a policy paper (Task 5.3). Furthermore, WP5 will present a structured overview of existing digital tools and solutions, accompanied by practical guidelines to support their adoption and scalability (Task 5.4).

WP5 tasks & deliverables				
#	Task	Timeframe	Participants	Deliverable
5.1	Creation of a repository of good practices	M6-36	ELTE + all partners	D5.1 Good practices repository [M15] 31 May 2025
5.2	Cross-border cooperation recommendations	M12-30	ELTE + all partners	D5.2 Cross-border cooperation recommendations [M30] 31 August 2026
5.3	Policy workshop on local FaCS-Tourism in rural and remote areas	M28-32	CERPHAAL + all partners	D5.3 Policy brief on local FaCS -Tourism [M28] 30 June 2026
5.4	ICT tools for FaCS-Tourism in rural and remote areas	M12-34	ARCTUR + all partners	D5.4 FaCS-Tourism digital tools overview and guidelines [M36] 28 Feb 2027

This deliverable establishes the foundation for a dynamic repository dedicated to collecting and sharing good practices in sustainable cultural tourism. Drawing primarily on outcomes from other WPs, particularly WP1 and WP2, as well as the pilot actions in WP3 and the research conducted in WP4, the repository is designed to evolve throughout the project’s lifecycle. To ensure consistency and usability, it includes the development of a common methodology and vocabulary, for identifying and reviewing practices. The repository serves a dual purpose: it functions as a structured

database to inform the recommendations developed in Task 5.2, and it offers a source of methodological inspiration for other initiatives and stakeholders. With contributions from all project partners, the repository reflects a wide range of expertise and regional perspectives.

2. Creation of the Good practices' repository

Definition of a SECreTour good practice

In the context of SECreTour, a good practice refers to a **specific practice or set of actions within an initiative**, rather than necessarily the initiative as a whole. While the definition stated in the Description of Action (DoA) emphasises *providers of solutions* – potentially suggesting entire initiatives – the adapted definition used in this deliverable focuses more precisely on **solution-oriented approaches** that promote fair, creative, and sustainable cultural tourism in rural and remote areas.

Accordingly, a *good practice* is not necessarily the full initiative, but rather the specific element(s) that demonstrably support sustainable cultural tourism objectives.

This distinction has been essential for shaping the structure of the repository, allowing for flexibility in documenting both targeted practices and broader initiatives, while ensuring the emphasis remains on what can be learned and transferred to other contexts.

Conception

To address the conceptual challenge of defining what constitutes a good practice, a **mixed approach** has been adopted for both the definition and organisation of the repository. This approach allows for the inclusion of both entire initiatives and the specific practices they encompass, ensuring flexibility while maintaining a focus on replicable, solution-oriented actions.

The repository is structured into **two main sections**:

- **Section 1: A fact sheet** that provides contextual information about the overarching initiative or organisation responsible for implementing the good practice(s).
- **Section 2: A structured, searchable database** of the identified good practices, including details on their practical applications in different contexts.

To ensure usability and clarity, the repository is designed to translate **heterogeneous data** collected across various work packages and pilot activities into a **structured, searchable format** that enables cross-comparison, thematic filtering, and practical reuse.

Workflow and methodology

The development of the SECreTour good practices repository follows a three-phase workflow to ensure systematic data collection, interpretation, and application of findings:

1. Data collection

- Pilot factsheets serve as a core internal source, documenting experiences of implementation of eight SECreTour pilots.
- An external survey—developed collaboratively by WP1, WP2, and WP4 (See *Annex 1*)—has been distributed to a wide range of initiatives using partners' networks.

- A dedicated interface on the project website has been created to facilitate external submissions, allowing stakeholders to contribute relevant good practices directly to the repository (See subchapter *Online submission form*).

2. Interpretation and presentation

- Collected data is reviewed and analysed to identify relevant good practices that align with SECreTour's and WPs' objectives.
- These practices are then structured and presented within the repository via the project website, ensuring clarity and accessibility.
- The repository follows the mixed approach outlined earlier, featuring both initiative-level fact sheets and searchable entries for specific practices and applications.

3. Analysis and recommendation development

- The identified good practices will contribute directly to the analytical work carried out under Task 5.2, which focuses on producing recommendations related to cross-border cooperation in sustainable cultural tourism.

Online submission form

As a key milestone in the SECreTour project (See *DoA, milestone n°5*), the online platform has introduced the possibility for external stakeholders to submit initiatives to the Good Practices Repository via a simplified submission form. Once submitted, the WP5 leader team reviews the entries, identifies qualifying good practices, and publishes them accordingly. (For details on the entries and website layout, see *Chapter 3*.)

Structure

Section 1: Factsheets of data providers

This section of the repository presents detailed factsheets for the initiatives that act as data providers – i.e., the sources of practical applications of good practices in sustainable cultural tourism.

For external initiatives, a dedicated subpage (similar in structure to the pilot pages) will be created. This ensures consistency and allows for a deeper understanding of each initiative's background and operational context. Each factsheet includes the following key elements:

- **General Information**
 - Location
 - Website and social media links
 - Contact information
- **Context**
 - Short narrative describing the origin and goals of the initiative
 - Type and status of the cultural or natural heritage involved
 - Associated tourism products, services, or locations
- **Communities and stakeholders**
 - Description of the heritage community and relevant stakeholders
- **Framework for sustainable cultural tourism**

- Governance model for resource and heritage management
- Planning and evaluation frameworks
- Good practices, replicable and scalable elements or processes
- **Transnational cooperation**
 - Cross-border or macro-regional partnerships or collaborative efforts involved.

These factsheets not only provide the necessary background for understanding the associated good practices but also serve as standalone references for users interested in replicating or learning from entire initiatives.

Section 2: Browsable collection of good practices and practical applications

The **initial structure and content** of the repository is based on the **pilot factsheets** developed earlier in the project, which provide a foundational reference for organising and contextualising the data.

The **thematic coverage and structure** of the repository are built upon a combination of **deductive and inductive approaches**, ensuring both methodological coherence and flexibility for ongoing updates:

- **Deductive approach.** A top-down method was used to establish the **main categories** and define the **overall scope** of the repository. The “**themes**” align with the objectives of WP1, WP2, and WP4. In parallel, more focused “**topics**” reflect the specific aims of the SECReTour project. This part of the structure is **static** and remains unchanged throughout the project to ensure consistency in classification and analysis.

Structure of Section 2 (themes & topics)	
Themes	Topics
Empowering local communities	Community engagement
	Mechanism for benefits sharing
Alternative business models	Participatory methodologies
	Digital technologies
	Mitigating tourism pressure
Transnational collaboration	Regional cooperation and networking
	Cross-border initiatives

- **Inductive approach.** In parallel, a bottom-up method is applied to identify and categorise **good practices** based on collected data. This component of the repository is **dynamic**, with new good practices being created and categorised as additional data is submitted and analysed, particularly from external contributions. Here, a distinction is made between:
 - **Practical applications.** Concrete examples of good practices implemented in a specific context (e.g., within a pilot or external initiative).
 - **Good practices (generalised level).** A broader conceptual category that may encompass multiple practical applications across different contexts.

This dual approach ensures that the repository remains grounded in the project's core objectives while being adaptable to new insights, fostering a growing and evolving body of knowledge on sustainable cultural tourism practices.

3. Web interface

The Good Practices Repository is accessible via the main navigation bar of the SECreTour project website (<https://secretourproject.eu/>).

By clicking the “Good practices” button, users are directed to a dedicated subpage: <https://secretourproject.eu/goodpractices>. This subpage features a **clickable tile-based design**, allowing users to visually browse through good practices. Each tile represents an identified good practice. To enhance discoverability, a drop-down menu allows users to filter good practices by theme: “Empowering local communities”, “Alternative business models” and “Transnational collaboration”.

Clicking on a good practice opens a standardised layout presenting its description, which includes:

- Filtering categories: themes, topics
- An extended title of the good practice
- A rationale or argument supporting its relevance
- Practical applications:
 - a brief description, and, where available, a bibliography
 - categorisation by country, with links to related pilots or external initiatives

Participatory heritage research

Categories

Empowering local communities • Community engagement

Mobilising action-research methodologies to develop heritage stewardship and foster community engagement, while also supporting communities in becoming active stakeholders and facilitating continuous dialogue among diverse participants

Argument

Participatory heritage research, grounded in action-research methodologies, is a powerful approach to fostering community engagement and promoting inclusive heritage stewardship. By involving local communities directly in processes such as mapping, documentation, and knowledge sharing, this method ensures that heritage practices reflect diverse voices and lived experiences. It supports communities in becoming active contributors, encouraging ownership and long-term commitment to heritage preservation. Through tools like collaborative mapping and oral history collection, participants co-create knowledge and identify valuable resources, both tangible and intangible, that may otherwise be overlooked. This continuous dialogue among stakeholders not only enriches the understanding of local heritage but also builds stronger social ties and more resilient, culturally aware communities.

Practical applications

France	+
Spain	+
Albania	+
Hungary	x
Initiative: Rural Roma Heritage communities	
Participatory research in heritage enhancement and documentation involves collaboration between researchers and representatives of the Roma Social Cooperative to plan and execute activities. Master students contribute to a special seminar, researching various themes alongside the youth of Tomor. The seminar will culminate in a workshop, where findings related to the gastronomic, musical, and family heritage of the Roma community will be presented.	
Bibliography	
György, E., & Oláh, G. (2018). The creation of resilient Roma cultural heritage. Case study of a bottom-up initiative from North-Eastern Hungary. <i>Socio.Hu, Special Issue</i> , 37–50. https://doi.org/10.18030/socio.hu.2018en.31	
Havasi, V. (2012). Community Development Initiatives in Peripheral Rural Territories of Borsod-Abaúj-Zemplén County. In J. Péntzes & Z. Radics (Eds.), <i>Roma population on the peripheries of the Visegrad countries: Spatial trends and social challenges</i> (pp. 188–205). Didakt.	
Ireland	+

To ensure visibility and ease of access, the repository is also linked directly from each pilot page, under the label “**Good practices identified**”. This feature allows users to view the practical applications associated with each pilot or initiative in context, promoting **cross-referencing** between the factsheets and the broader database of good practices.

Good practices identified

External submission in the Good Practices Repository

The external submission can be accessed through the main navigation bar of the SE-CreTour project website. To locate it, place the cursor on the “Good practices” menu item to display a drop-down menu, then select “Submit a case study”.

Another option for submitting case studies is available within the Good Practices catalogue, as well as on each individual Good Practice page. In these cases, users will see the following prompt:

Do you know other examples of Good practices in Sustainable Cultural Tourism?

Help us expand the catalogue

This is followed by a “Submit a case study” button, which directs users to the submission form.

Do you know other examples of Good practices in Sustainable Cultural Tourism?

Help us to expand the catalogue

Submit a case study

The submission form begins with a **brief description to clarify the type of contributions being requested**. This is presented as a collapsible field containing the same introductory text used in the external survey (see *Annex 1*).

Home > Good practices > Submit a case study

Submit a case study

▼ Introduction

What is SECReTOUR about?

SECReTOUR (<https://secretourproject.eu/>), standing for Sustainable, Engaging and Creative TOURism, is a research project funded by the Horizon Europe program that seeks to identify ways of making tourism a tool for the sustainable and inclusive development of rural areas. SECReTOUR draws on concepts such as cultural tourism, heritage communities, territorial communities and territorial entrepreneurship.

What is the topic of our survey?

Assess the extent to which the organisation of local residents and stakeholders into communities federated by the preservation of a local resource or a shared attachment can be a lever for the sustainable management of rural areas.

What are we interested in?

Successful or inspiring case-studies of people living in rural territories and organised as a community (formalized or not formalized) to manage resources of their territories to which they have a shared attachment: a typical agricultural or culinary product, a know-how or tradition, a shared-use infrastructure (paths, irrigation channels, etc), or any kind of heritage resource.

What do we expect from you?

We would be grateful if you could describe one (or more) inspiring case study(ies) using the following questionnaire format. If you wish, this questionnaire can be completed during an interview with a member of the SECReTOUR team.

The next section, **General Information**, includes fields for the name of the initiative or organization, location, and website or social media links. The interface allows multiple entries for the website and social media fields.

▶ Introduction

General information

Name of initiative/organisation *

As they refer to themselves

Location (village/town, region, country) *

Provide the necessary details on the location; use coordinates for remote areas.

Website/social media

If available, provide links to associated websites and social media

The following section of the survey focuses on providing **context** regarding the origin and objectives of the initiative, the cultural or natural heritage managed collectively, and the associated tourism products and services. A small question mark icon is placed next to each entry field title, offering guiding or support questions to assist respondents in providing relevant information.

Context

Origin and goals of the initiative ⓘ *

Cultural or natural heritage managed collectively
What are the resources managed collectively?
To which extent are they endangered?

Provide a short narrative description

Cultural or natural heritage managed collectively ⓘ *

Describe the cultural or natural heritage managed collectively

Associated tourism products, services, or locations ⓘ *

Describe the tourism products, services, or locations associated with the resource managed collectively.

Two sections follow: one dedicated to the description of the **communities and relevant stakeholders** involved, and another focusing on **transnational cooperation**, highlighting any cross-border partnerships or collaborative efforts.

Communities & stakeholders

Heritage community and relevant stakeholders ⓘ *

Transnational cooperation

Cross-border partnerships or collaborative efforts involved ⓘ

Describe any international connections or activities the initiative is involved in, and explain how these collaborations work and what benefits they bring.

The final steps to complete the form include the option to upload up to five **images** and to provide **contact information** (name, organization, and email address). Before submission, users must accept the **Disclaimer, Privacy Policy, and Data Protection Information**. A statement related to Data Protection Information is displayed for review:

“Data Protection information: The Controller for the processing of personal data is Eachtra Archaeological Projects Ltd. The purpose of processing is managing services to the scientific and technological community, management of participants, management of activities, management of registered individuals, and management of surveys.”

The form is completed by clicking the “Submit” button located at the bottom of the page.

Images

+ Upload image

Provide up to 5 representative images of good resolution showcasing the initiative

Maximum 5 files.

10 MB limit.

Allowed types: gif, jpg, jpeg, png.

Contact information

Please provide your contact information in case we need to reach out for further details

Name

Company

Email *

I have read and accept the [Disclaimer](#) and [Privacy Policy](#), as well as the [Data Protection Information](#)

Data Protection information: The Controller for the processing of personal data is Eachtra Archaeological Projects Ltd. The purpose of processing is managing services to the scientific and technological community, management of participants, management of activities, management of registered individuals, and management of surveys.

Submit

Once the user submits the form, a **confirmation** message is displayed, and the system automatically send an email containing all the submitted information to both the WP5 team and the user.

Thank you so much for your time and input — your feedback means the world to us!

You may be contacted after the review if additional information is needed.

A copy of your answers has been sent to the provided e-mail address.

The WP5 team will then review the request. If needed, the user may be contacted to provide additional details, particularly regarding the “Framework for sustainable cultural tourism”, to gain a clearer understanding of the developed business model. Upon approval, the information can be made public by creating a new initiative page and updating the corresponding good practices pages.

4. Plan to achieve the KPI

The KPI in the DoA establishes a threshold range of **20 to 50 good practices to be collected** and published through the Good Practices Repository.

To achieve this target, data collection efforts are being actively intensified through multiple channels:

- Continued dissemination of **external survey**, developed in collaboration with WP1, WP2, and WP4, targeting a broad range of initiatives.
- **Mobilisation of partners' networks** to reach relevant stakeholders and encourage contributions.
- Promotion and maintenance of the **online submission interface** on the project website, designed to facilitate user-friendly external input.

These efforts are complemented by internal contributions from pilot activities and the ongoing identification of additional practices during project implementation, ensuring both quantitative and qualitative fulfilment of the KPI.

5. Conclusion

The Good Practices Repository developed under WP5 plays a central role in capturing and disseminating practical, solution-oriented approaches to sustainable cultural tourism across rural and remote areas. By adopting a mixed approach – documenting both entire initiatives and their specific practices – the repository ensures flexibility while maintaining a consistent, structured framework rooted in the project's objectives. Drawing on pilot factsheets, external submissions, and thematic insights from other work packages, it provides a dynamic and evolving knowledge base. Its web-based, tile-designed interface and searchable structure make the repository both accessible and user-friendly, serving as a resource for stakeholders seeking inspiration, guidance, or transferability.

Looking ahead, the repository serves not only as a platform for collecting and showcasing good practices, but also as a strategic asset for shaping recommendations, promoting cross-border cooperation, and supporting the development of macro-regional cultural tourism policies under Task 5.2. It reflects the SECreTour project's broader ambition to contribute to a more balanced, inclusive, and sustainable tourism landscape.

6. Annex 1: Survey of heritage communities in rural Europe

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What we expect from you:

We would be grateful if you could describe one (or more) inspiring case study(ies) using the following questionnaire format.

If you wish, this questionnaire can be completed during an interview with a member of the SECReTOUR team.

Contacts

- Antonella Fresa, General Manager at PROMOTER, fresa@promoter.it
- Flore Coppin, SECReTOUR project manager at BIBRACTE
- Carsten Jacob Humlebæk, Associate professor, Ph.D., Copenhagen Business School

Survey of heritage communities in rural Europe

Fact sheet

Name of the case study:

Geographical location of the case study:

- (1) What is the territorial context of the case study regarding economic, social and ecological issues? What role does tourism play in this context?
- (2) What are the resources managed collectively? To which extend are they endangered? (Please describe them as precisely as possible)
- (3) What is the composition of the community attached to this resource (local and/or national dimension, sociological composition, age groups, and so on)?
- (4) What means of action are used by the community? Since when? Are these actions based on a historical tradition (alive or revived) or, on the contrary, created ex-nihilo as part of a project of reactivation?
- (5) Is the community organised to jointly manage the heritage resource? If yes, to what extent is it active? What is its governance?
- (6) Has the community already a relationship in place with the local population and the public authorities? If yes, how has it evolved over the short and long term?"
- (7) Is the community (or has it been in the past) part of a network of similar communities?
- (8) What are the successes and achievements of the community? To what extend are they connected with tourism issues?
- (9) What socio-economic model sustains the community and its resource? How stable is it, and what are the key threats? What strategies and opportunities exist to strengthen the resources and the associated community?

To finish, please indicate where we can find out more information about the case study (coordinates of the community or of some of its key members, web pages, articles, etc).

Name, position and e-mail address of the writer of the fact sheet:

Date of completion of the fact sheet: